

REHABEND

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CONSTRUCTION PATHOLOGY, REHABILITATION TECHNOLOGY
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FEASIBILITY OF DEFECT DETECTION IN CONCRETE CYLINDERS BY MEANS OF MUON SCATTERING RADIOGRAPHY (MSR)

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MUON
systems

IFCA

INTRODUCTION

Cosmic rays interact with the atmosphere creating muons, among other particles

Muons arrive with an approximately **constant flux** to the earth surface ($\sim 10000 \mu/m^2min$)

We measure their **scattering angle** ($\Delta\theta$) which is related to the traversed material

R.L. Workman et al. (Particle Data Group), to be published in Prog. Theor. Exp. Phys. 2022, 083C01 (2022)

Using cosmic muons

Muon Absorption Radiography (MAR)

Number of detectors: 1

Measurement: unique trajectory, muon flux

Application: Large objects, long time

Muon Scattering Radiography (MSR):

Number of detectors: 2

Measurement: in and out trajectories, deviation

Application: Smaller objects, short time

Features of Muon Radiography (MR)

Natural Radiation

Constant Flux

Detection

Reconstruction

Non-destructive, no need of physical contact with the target
Natural radiation, innocuous
Highly penetrating
Continuous monitoring

Review of applications

Applications of MR in archaeology and civil structures:

- First application of MR:
 - Inspection of the overburden of a tunnel
- Applications of MSR
 - Inspection in the dome of Florence Cathedral (Italy): **reinforcement element assessment.**
- Applications of MAR
 - Search of **hidden chambers, cavities, or voids**: Pyramids of Giza (Egypt), Aztec Pyramid of the Sun at Teotihuacan (Mexico), La Milpa Mayan site (Belize), Mount Echia in Naples (Italy).

All these researches proved the **potential of MR to explore the state of buildings and structures in a non-destructive way.**

Motivation of our research

- Establish MSR as a **Non-Destructive Testing technique** for deterioration and defect detection in **concrete structures**.
- MSR is also useful for the inspection of **delicate structures**, such as monuments or ancient buildings.
- We have focused this study on the detection of **subtle defects** in small concrete structures.
- Specifically, on **full transverse cracks** in 15 cm diameter **concrete cylindrical samples**.

DEVELOPMENT

- **Detectors:**

- ❑ Composed of **four MWPC** (Multi Wire Proportional Chamber)
- ❑ Each chamber has two perpendicular **layers with 224 wires**, inside an **electric field** and a **gas atmosphere**
- ❑ **Wires separated by 4 mm**, they detect charged particles
- ❑ **Synchronization electronics** identify a muon when signals are obtained “at the same time” in all the chambers

Samples and scenarios

- **Samples:** Two concrete samples (A and B). Cylindrical-shaped, diameter of 15 cm and height of 30 cm.

Sample	Mass (Kg)	Volume (cm ³)	Density (g/cm ³)
A	11.35	5300	2.14
B	12.90	5300	2.43

- **First scenario:** unique concrete cylinder (sample A). Intact concrete structure.
- **Second scenario:** two concrete cylinders. Cracked concrete structure (aperture of 2 cm and 1 cm).
- **Scanned volume:** the 20 central centimetres along the longitudinal axis of the cylinder.

Algorithms

- **POCA (Point Of Closest Approach) algorithm evaluation:**

- Limitations** correctly estimating the interaction point of **small deviation muons**.
- Loss of useful information** for the detection of small defects in medium density and medium size objects.

- **Proposed algorithm:**

- Statistical analysis of the **deviations of all muons crossing the target**.
- Divides the target volume in **1 cm wide vertical sections**

RESULTS

- 1 and 2 cm aperture full transversal cracks have been detected.
- The muons passing the vertical sections where the cracks are located have **statistically the smallest deviations**.

- Measurements of **15 h of data taking time**.

RESULTS

- **Other 2 cm crack has been set up, moving its location 3 cm to the negative side of the longitudinal axis.**
- The crack has been **clearly imaged once again**, but like a **1 cm aperture defect**.
- The highest deviations in all the reconstructions **highlight the location of sample B**, the sample with the higher density.

DISCUSSION

- **The cracks and their locations have been detected** in all the measurements.
- **The aperture of the cracks have been imaged**, with an error of 1 cm in the fourth measurement.
- Regarding the **data taking time** of the measurements:
 - ❑ The presence of background noise has required **to filter** the detected events, **losing part of the muon flux**.
 - ❑ However, the results are promising and **if the efficiency is improved, the necessary data taking time will be directly reduced**. Ongoing work!

CONCLUSIONS

- **The absence of concrete cylindrical sections of 1 cm (0.4 Kg) and 2 cm (0.8 Kg) wide have been detected by means of MSR.**
- **The reconstruction algorithm has located the cracks and has estimated their aperture.**
- **In addition, the higher density (+0.29 g/cm³) of one of the samples has been clearly detected.**
- **Future work:** additional chambers, Smart Tracking algorithms, and innovative image reconstruction algorithms.
- **Muon Scattering Radiography** is a promising NDT technique **applicable in concrete structures** and **capable of finding small defects** in centimetre scale.

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THANKS FOR YOUR ATTENTION,
I LOOK FORWARD TO RECEIVING ANY QUESTIONS OR
COMMENTS

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